

MEDICINAL OF PLANTS CHRONIC IN CHOLECYSTITIS IMPORTANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14500916>

Conclusion : Last ten year within , both local and international scale , food digestion to do system functional violations treatment for new effective tools current to grow with in treatment achieved to achievements despite , despite roads system diseases appearance in being noticeable growth Pathologies associated with the biliary tract and pancreas pose great challenges to modern medicine, a trend that shows stability .

Key words : diagnosis , prevention to take chronic cholecystitis , treatment , medicinal plants

Abstract : This of the disease polyethological and pathogenesis mechanisms abundance him/her to correct various approaches demand does . Such without , naturally come output components own inside received herbal remedies main therapy with together separately attention is worthy . Curcumin farnesoid X receptor through from cholestasis protection to the effect yes , this bile acid homeostasis to restore and inflammation reactions against to stand and as a result cholestasis to decrease take comes . One row research this showed that curcumin grass bubble reduction to the ability has . Many numerical various kind useful features to the existence despite the fact that curcumin medical in practice wide application close until then with its low bioavailability limited was . Kavacurcumin such as biological existence high was forms synthesis made from ex . use Grass roads and stomach under diaper pathology modern medicine for current is a problem . The last ten annually Pharmacological research both in Uzbekistan and abroad at the market food digestion to do system functional violations correction for new effective medicine of tools appearance to be with related known therapeutic to success despite the disease increase trend being observed . biliary from the system . From this except this trend stability with separated It stands . So scientific to forecasts according to , the next 15-20 years inside food digestion to do system diseases stress, dyskinetic , metabolic in the world to diseases based diseases number increase on account of at least 30-50% increases. mechanisms . There are chronic acalculous cholecystitis and chronic calculous cholecystitis. Currently, the prevailing opinion is mainly about the progressive development of gallbladder diseases. Functional motor-tonic

disorders (dyskinesia) of the biliary tract, respectively, of a hyperkinetic (hypertensive) or hypokinetic (hypotonic) type, occur with an increase or decrease in tone. contractile (motor) activity of the gallbladder, often contributing to stagnation, changes in physicochemical properties and infection of bile in the gallbladder. A chronic inflammatory process develops, affecting its mucous membrane and wall. In most cases, the formation of cholesterol, bilirubin and mixed gallstones occurs, often accompanied by stony cholecystitis, which is often diagnosed with gallstone disease . In most cases, it develops against the background of a bacterial infection that enters the gallbladder by enterogenic (ascending from the intestine), hematogenous (from foci of chronic infection) or lymphogenous route. The development of the disease is facilitated by stagnation bile in the gallbladder, mainly due to hypokinetic biliary dyskinesia, anomalies in their development, a sedentary lifestyle (inactivity), errors in nutrition (excessive consumption of fats and fried foods, easily digestible carbohydrates, insufficient consumption of vegetable fiber, etc.), rare meals, obesity, repeated pregnancies, constipation, etc. In the initial stage of chronic cholecystitis, the inflammatory process, initiated by bacterial and other flora, affects the mucous and submucosal membranes of the gallbladder. In the future, inflammatory infiltration spreads to the entire gallbladder wall with the development of connective tissue (fibrosis) and thickening of its wall; damage to the serosa. The clinical picture of chronic cholecystitis consists of pain, dyspeptic and neurotic syndromes. The nature of the pain depends to some extent on dyskinesia of the common bile ducts: in the hypotonic variant it can be constant or periodic, dull or aching, in the case of hypertension - short-term, more intense, cramping. The pain is localized in the right hypochondrium and epigastric region and can radiate to the right shoulder blade, collarbone, shoulder and lumbar region. With the above-described irradiation, unbearable, very strong, cramping pains in the right hypochondrium - biliary colic - are characteristic of HCG and often occur as a result of blockage of the gallbladder neck or extrahepatic bile ducts with stones. The pain syndrome is provoked by the consumption of fatty, fried, smoked, spicy foods, carbonated drinks; heavy physical exertion (lifting and lifting heavy loads, physical exercises with a bent torso, etc.), body shaking (riding in shaking vehicles, etc.), psychoemotional stressful situations. Dyspeptic syndrome is characterized by nausea, belching, bitterness in the mouth, bloating, stool disorders (constipation or diarrhea) and decreased appetite. Vomiting is very rare. Typical manifestations of neurotic syndrome - conflict, inconsistency and a tendency to introspection. When

examining the patient, it is often found that the sclera is subicteric and the tongue is superimposed. With the help of palpation and percussion, pain points and zones caused by irritation of the autonomic nervous system are identified. The exacerbation of the disease is indicated by the presence of pain in the gallbladder point (intersection of the right costal arch with the outer edge of the rectus abdominis muscle), as well as pain in the area of attachment of the gallbladder under the right shoulder blade. XI-XII ribs to the spine. They indicate the presence of pain during palpation at the gallbladder point during breathing or at the height of deep inspiration. Drug-free treatment provides for a rational alternation of rest and physical activity (morning exercises, swimming, walks in the fresh air, etc.), physiotherapy, phytotherapy, the use of mineral waters and therapeutic nutrition. Usually, a 5-day schedule is prescribed with frequent (4-5 times a day) meals in small portions.

Diet therapy is an important component of treatment, helping to stimulate bile secretion, reduce the activity of the inflammatory process in the gallbladder and prevent the formation of stones. Frequent, fractional, mechanically and chemically soft nutrition improves the emptying of the gallbladder by stimulating its motor evacuation functions. Individual tolerance to food is taken into account. The amount of fat in the diet is limited to a sufficient amount (normal) of proteins and carbohydrates. Limit or limit the use of fatty, fried foods, pickled and salty dishes, spicy spices, foods rich in cholesterol (salmon, egg yolk, nuts,) An important component of treatment is helping to stimulate bile secretion, reduce the activity of the inflammatory process. disrupts the gallbladder and prevents the formation of stones. Frequent, fractional, mechanically and chemically soft nutrition improves the emptying of the gallbladder by stimulating its motor evacuation functions. Individual tolerance to food is taken into account. The amount of fat in the diet is limited to a sufficient (normal) amount of proteins and carbohydrates. Limit or limit the use of fatty, fried, smoked and salty dishes, spicy spices, foods rich in cholesterol (salmon, egg yolk, nuts, red and black caviar), cakes and pastries, creams, alcoholic and carbonated drinks. They increase the proportion of vegetables and fruits, vegetable oils (olive, sunflower, corn, etc.) with a normal diet. low-fat meat, poultry, fish, dairy products - milk, cottage cheese, etc. The treatment of chronic cholecystitis depends on the type of concomitant biliary dyskinesia, the absence or presence of stones in the gallbladder and extrahepatic bile ducts, and the severity of the disease. For a relatively mild clinical course of exacerbation, short courses (5-7 days) of antibacterial therapy with tetracyclines

(metacycline, doxycycline, etc.) and fluoroquinolone drugs (norfloxacin, iprofloxacin, etc.), sulfonamides (biseptol, etc.), nitrofurantoin derivatives (furagin, ercefuryl, etc.) are used for internal use. For a severe course of exacerbation, fluoroquinolone antibiotics (levofloxacin, pefloxacin), cephalosporins (ceftriaxone, ceftazidime, cefepime, etc.), aminoglycosides (amikacin, tobramycin, etc.), semi-synthetic penicillins (amoxiclav, timentin, etc.) are indicated for parenteral use. To eliminate bile stasis, drugs that enhance the peristalsis of the biliary tract (olive oil, sea buckthorn, magnesia) are used. Cholagogues (drugs that increase bile secretion) are used with caution so as not to increase pain and lead to an increase in stasis. During the period of exacerbation of chronic uncomplicated cholecystitis, phytotherapy methods are used for treatment: herbs (mint, valerian, dandelion, chamomile), calendula flowers. Exacerbation signs from decreasing and disease into remission from the past then, magnesia, xylitol or sorbitol with tubes recommendation Chronic cholecystitis phytotherapeutic therapy with tansy, yarrow, marshmallow, yarrow prepared tinctures acceptance from doing consists of. Physiotherapy used: reflexology, electrophoresis, SMT therapy, mud therapy and others Balneological at resorts sanatorium treatment is displayed.

Conclusion:

The study sheds light on the use of traditional health systems in the treatment of chronic diseases in Bukhara. Given the persistent mortality rates associated with these diseases, there is a need for phytochemical and pharmacological studies on various medicinal plant species. There is a need to expand access to traditional medicine, especially in rural areas. In addition, endangered species require special attention to ensure sustainable traditional phytotherapy methods. The literature on the treatment of cholecystitis requires quality improvement and evidence-based evaluation, and cognitive medicine serves as a valuable additional evaluation tool.

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